

to April, has scanty or little rainfall. Coconut is the most important crop. Rice, grown on about 14,000 ha, is second. Most rice is grown in low-lying areas with adequate rainfall, but rice is also grown as a direct-seeded upland crop.

More than 70% of the rice area is planted to the local variety C 14-8, which matures in about 200 days. C 14-8 is transplanted from July to September and harvested about December. It yields from 1.2 to 1.5 t/ha. Farmers prefer it because it offers one or two tiller cuttings which they use as green fodder for cattle. The variety is also fairly resistant to some common diseases and insects.

Over the last decade, the local Department of Agriculture has introduced some high yielding, short-duration varieties such as IR8, Jaya, and Ratna; however, these varieties have not spread as much as desired. Realizing the vast potential of the region, ICAR has established a research center for all aspects of crop, animal, and fishery sciences. Rice productivity may be increased by 5 to 6 times the present average yield. Short-duration varieties would ensure the growing of two crops per year. Preliminary trials with many of the hybrids obtained from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project have shown that an average yield of 3 to 4 t/ha per season can easily be harvested. RPA5824, RPA 5929, IET2914, IET4097, and IET4554 yielded more than 7 t/ha in 1976 varietal trials. Because the first crop was harvested under wet conditions, seeds of many of the hybrids germinated before harvest. Incorporation of seed dormancy in early maturing varieties would be of major importance.

Basic fertilizer recommendations are not yet available for rice, so recommendations for mainland regions are usually adopted (60 kg/ha of N, P₂O₅, K₂O). Alkaline intensity varies. Fertilization experiments are in progress.

Heavy rainfall and high humidity most of the year favor weed growth. About 60% of the weeds in rice fields are monocots. Hand weeding is the best control method, but it increases production costs. Herbicide experiments

are in progress.

The first crop generally does not suffer from major rice pests, although stem borers, case worms, and hoppers are sporadically noticed. The second crop is subject to heavy infestation of *Leptocorisa varicornis*, which causes serious yield loss. Blast was serious in 1976. A large number of weevils and other insects infest the seeds of rice hybrids, reducing seed germination and storage value. The stand of seeds that do germinate is also reduced.

Preliminary observations indicated that dried neem leaves *Azadirachta indica* prevent damage of stored seed. While

fungicides and insecticides can be of value, their large-scale use would probably be a health hazard. Therefore, a study is undertaken to determine the best method of storing grains to ensure high germination and minimum storage loss.

A hybridization program using C 14-8 and some early maturing varieties has also been initiated. Large areas remain fallow because of salinity from inundation with sea water. Identification of crops that can tolerate salinity will contribute significantly to the development of rice-based cropping systems.

Sociological and professional characteristics of Asian rice breeders

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As part of an IRRI study on rice breeding programs in Asia, a survey was made of the sociological and professional characteristics of 40 rice breeders at 27 research centers in 10 Asian nations. The project was conducted in collaboration with the Agricultural Education Department, Iowa State University, USA, and was partially funded by a research grant from The Rockefeller Foundation.

The mean age of breeders was 41.9 years, ranging from 31 to 55 years. Seventy percent of the breeders were between the ages of 37 and 47. Fifty-three percent came from agricultural backgrounds (when they were growing up more than half of their family income was derived from agricultural sources). Of the latter, 95% came from families that owned their land. Fifty-five percent indicated that their families owned the land and farmed it themselves; 40% rented or sharecropped most of their land to other farmers. One respondent's family had rented land.

The mean number of years of professional experience (excluding academic work) of the rice breeders surveyed was 13.9, ranging from 2 to 33 years. Twenty-six percent had 10 years or less of experience; 28% had 20 years or more.

How rice breeders allocate their professional time among different types of work. Thirty-eight scientists at 27 experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Eighty-five percent of the breeders indicated that they worked only with rice; 15% worked with rice and other crops, including wheat, pulses, maize, and potatoes.

To determine how scientists allocated their professional time among various activities, 38 of the breeders were asked to indicate the percentages of their time that they spent in several aspects of rice work. The mean percentages were then calculated for each activity. The breeders spent a mean percentage of 68.4% of their work time in research; 56.1% of the total time was in breeding-related activities (crossing, selecting, evaluating experimental lines, etc.) (see figure). Fifteen percent of their time went into

administrative work; 5.7% went into teaching and training; 4.7% into extension; 4% into writing for publication; and 2.2% into other activities. *W*

Genetic potential and utilization of rice in northeastern India

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Rices grown in northeastern India were collected to determine what germ plasm is available there and its potential. The rices were grown in a randomized block at the botanical garden of North Eastern Hill University, Shillong, and the mean height, yield, grain fineness, seed protein content, and protein yield per plant were determined. Three replications of 30 plants/replication per genotype were used. The mean values computed for various traits are depicted in Figures 1 and 2. The average shoot height of the rices ranged from 71 to 102 cm. Kba Saw rut B-2, Dullo-X, and Lyngri were the tallest varieties, with shoot heights of 102, 101, and 101 cm, respectively. Theuru red was the shortestest, 71 cm. Most of the rices were coarse-grained. Kba Saw rut B-2 had the finest grains and Lyngri, the coarsest.

The rices varied greatly in yield. Abar-B yielded highest followed by Ryllowhite. Local Beach-A yielded lowest. The crude seed protein content varied similarly. The highest protein level, 12.7%, was in Theuru red; the lowest, in Abar-B. But Abar-B had the best seed protein production per plant, closely followed by Ryllowhite. Fortunately, these two varieties have other desirable traits such as medium height, medium tillering, and heavy grain weight. Abar-B seems to be the best because of its high grain number per panicle, grain yield, and tiller production, along with its seed protein production. Abar-B also has high consumer preference and is well-adapted to the region's varying soil types and prevalent climatic conditions.

Furthermore, most of the inhabitants of the Northeastern Himalayan region are tribal people who are nonvegetarian, so

1. Performance of rice varieties: 1 = Abar-A, 2 = Abar-B, 3 = Abar red-A, 4 = Abar red-B, 5 = Ryllo red-1, 6 = Ryllo red-3, 7 = Ryllo red-4, 8 = Ryllo red-5, 9 = Ryllo red-6, 10 = Ryllowhite, 11 = Dullo-A, 12 = Dullo-6, 13 = Dullo-8, 14 = Dullo-X, 15 = Dullo XI, 16 = Kba Saw rut B-2, 17 = Kba Saw rut B-4, 18 = Nanglwai, 19 = Local Beach-A, 20 = Kuki, 21 = Theuru red, 22 = Lyngri, 23 = Keiba Thangamaa 24 = Tangla

2. Seed protein content and production. Kurukshetra University, India. (For names of varieties, see caption of Figure 1.)